

BIODEGRADATION POTENTIALS OF SOIL MICROBIOTA ISOLATED FROM NPDC FLOW STATION FLARE SITE, OLOGBOON FORCADOS BLEND CRUDE OIL

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ABSTRACT

The biodegradation potentials of microbiota isolated from top soils collected in the vicinities of two gas flare sites at Ologbo town, Edo State and a fallow farmland in Benin City on Forcados blended crude oil was determined. Serial dilution and pour plate methods were utilized in the isolation and enumeration of the microbial load of the soils. The heterotrophic bacterial and fungal counts varied from 0.4×10^3 cfu/g to 1.5×10^3 cfu/g and 0.2×10^3 cfu/g to 1.8×10^3 cfu/g respectively. The differences in the microbial counts were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). Ten (10) bacterial and 10 fungal isolates were identified. All the soils were sandy. *Aeromonas* sp., *Bacillus* sp., *Corynebacterium* sp., *Penicillium* sp. and the bacterial consortium had the best biodegradation potentials. *Aeromonas* sp. effected maximal reduction in the TPH (DRO) content of the blended petroleum portion of the growth medium. Soils surrounding gas flare pits are a viable source of hydrocarbonoclastic bacteria and fungi.

KEYWORDS: *biodegradation potentials, Gas flare sites, microbiota, Ologbo town, hydrocarbonoclastic*

INTRODUCTION

Flaring of associated gas is the process of combustible vapors from an oil well, either as a means of disposal or as a safety measure to relieve well pressure. Nigeria is known to flare about 50% of her total associated gas produced which is about 850 billion cubic feet per year (Bcf/y). Gas flaring releases large amounts of methane, which has a high global warming potential (Ubani and Onyejekwe, 2013). The methane is accompanied by another major greenhouse gas, carbon (IV) oxide, of which Nigeria was estimated to have emitted more than 34.38 million metric tons in 2002, accounting for about 50% of all industrial emissions in the country and 30% of the total CO₂ emission (Beychok, 2005). Kindzierski (2000) reported that during the gas flaring process, complete combustion though rarely achieved, can release relatively innocuous gases such as carbon (IV) oxide and water. However, the author also stated that incomplete combustion emits various compounds such as methane, propane, and hazardous air pollutants such as volatile organic compounds (VOCs), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and soot. Strosher (2000) opined that flaring can also produce soot and other pollutant species that have negative effects on air quality and the environment. Humans exposed to such substances can suffer from a variety of respiratory problems. Benzene, known to be emitted from gas flares in

undocumented quantities is well recognized as a cause for leukemia and other blood-related diseases (Vidali, 2001). However, these polluted environments can serve as a source of hydrocarbonoclastic microorganisms which could be used for bioremediation purposes.

The aims of this study were the isolation and identification of heterotrophic and hydrocarbonoclastic microorganisms from soils exposed to gas flaring (Flare site, NPDC flow-station, Ologbo, Edo State). Evaluation of the physicochemical properties of the exposed soils. Screening of the isolates for their ability to utilize Forcados blended crude-oil as sole carbon source and evaluating the biodegradation potentials of the respective microbial isolates which had given positive results at the end of the respective screening tests.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection

Top soil samples (50g) were collected from three (3) respective sampling points each at two (2) gas flaring sites located within NPDC Flow-Station, Ologbo town, Ikpoba Okha Local Government Area in Edo State, Southern Nigeria, using a soil auger. The sampling points were located in the vicinity of a new gas flaring site (14 months after commencement of flaring) and an older gas flaring site (over 7 years of flaring activity). The samples were bored at a 5m interval from the flare pipe and were labeled as; O₁ (5m), O₂ (10m), O₃(15m), N₁(5m), N₂(10m) and N₃(15m) respectively. A control soil sample labeled as CO was also obtained from a fallow farmland located within the premises of P2, P-Quarters, University of Benin, Benin City. The soils were collected in the month of March, 2012. Also, Forcados blended crude oil used for analysis was collected from NPDC flow station at Ologbo town. The collected soil samples at each boring were transferred into sterile labelled polyethylene bags.

Isolation and enumeration of heterotrophic and hydrocarbonoclastic soil microflora using general and enriched media

Serial ten-fold dilutions of 1 g of the respective soil samples were prepared in peptone water up to 10⁻⁶ dilution, and aliquots (0.1 ml) of each dilution were cultured on plates of Nutrient Agar for mean heterotrophic bacterial count and Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) for mean heterotrophic fungal count, by pour plate method (Sharma, 2009). Mineral salt agar (MSA) (Mills *et al.* 1978), modified by the addition of 1% (v/v) Forcados blended crude oil was used for the isolation of hydrocarbonoclastic soil bacteria and fungi. The modified MSA were supplemented with 10mg/ml Nystatin and 10 mg/ml Chloramphenicol for the selective enumeration of hydrocarbonoclastic bacteria and fungi respectively (Mills *et al.* 1978). Plating was done in duplicates. The culture plates were incubated at 35⁰C for 48 h and ambient room temperature of 28 ±2⁰C for 5 days in respect of the total heterotrophic bacterial, hydrocarbon utilizing bacterial, fungal and hydrocarbon utilizing fungal counts respectively.

Characterization of the soil microbiota: Representative bacterial and fungal colonies were sub-cultured on freshly prepared nutrient agar and potato dextrose agar plates. These plates were incubated at 35°C for 24 h and room temperature ($28\pm 2^{\circ}$ C) for 2 days for bacterial and fungal cultures respectively. The colonial characteristics of the sub-cultured bacterial colonies were recorded. The bacterial isolates were further identified by the identification schemes of Holt *et al.* (1994) and Sharma (2009). The sub cultured fungal isolates were identified on the basis of their morphological and microscopic features. Their microscopic attributes were examined using the wet mount technique (Choi *et al.* 1999; Sharma, 2009). Lactophenol-cotton blue was utilized as stain-mountant. The microscopic structures observed were recorded and compared to those described by Alexopoluloset *al.* (1996).

Preparation of standard cultures for axenic bacterial isolates: Standard cultures were prepared for the isolates adapting the methods of Gerhardt *et al.* (1994) and Seely and Van-Denmark (1981). The plate counts were recorded and the values obtained were expressed as standard number of cells present in 0.1ml of the broth. This was used as the standardized culture.

Physicochemical analyses of various soil samples: With the exception of moisture content analysis, the respective soil samples were placed on large wooden trays and air-dried for 72 hr. Lumps of moist soil samples were broken by hand prior to air drying of the samples. The air dried samples were also sieved using a 2mm mesh. Parameters which included moisture content, pH, particle size distribution and Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC) were determined according to methods described by Radojevic and Bashkin, (1999). The Total Organic Carbon (TOC), total Nitrogen and Total Hydrocarbon Content (THC) of the soil samples were also evaluated in accordance with procedures stated by Radojevic and Bashkin, (1999) and Bremmer and Mulvaney (1982). The lead (Pb), zinc (Zn) and cadmium (Cd) content of the soils were determined using method described by Radojevic and Bashkin (1999) using a Digester (Gerhardt digester, UK.), and Atomic Absorbance Spectrophotometer (AAS) (Buck Scientific model 210 VGP USA) .

Screening for the ability of the microbial isolates to utilize blended crude oil as sole carbon and energy sources

About 500 ml of mineral salt medium was prepared and 0.5g of 2,6 Dichlorophenol Indophenol (2,6 DCPIP) (redox indicator) was added to the medium. The mixture was stirred to ensure proper mixing (Bidolaet *al.*, 2010). The resultant medium had a dark blue coloration. Nine (9) ml of the medium was dispensed into two sets of six test tubes. One (1) ml of crude oil (Forcados blend) was also added to each tube and sterilized. On cooling, the first set of test tubes were inoculated with 0.1ml of standardized bacterial cell suspension of the respective bacterial isolates. The second set of test tubes were inoculated with one agar plug of the respective purified fungal isolates (collected with the aid of a sterile 4mm cork borer and forceps) (George-Okafor *et al.*, 2009). An un-inoculated test tube served as control. The tubes were incubated at 37°C for 7 days (George-Okafor *et al.*, 2009) and monitored daily for color change from deep blue to colorless.

Evaluation of the growth profile of axenic and mixed consortium of fungal isolates in blended petroleum medium

Two (2) litres of mineral salt medium was prepared and 2 g of 2, 6, Dichlorophenol Indophenol (DCPIP) was added to the medium (Bidola *et al.*, 2010) and stirred to ensure development of a deep blue coloration of the medium (Enabulele and Obayagbona, 2013). About 247.5 ml of the medium was dispensed into several 250 ml conical flasks and 2.5 ml of blended crude oil was added to each flask and sterilized at 121^oC for 15 minutes. Upon cooling, 2 ml of a 24 hr mineral salt medium (MSM) broth culture of the respective bacterial isolates and 96 hr MSM broth culture of the fungi isolates were pipetted into each respective flask except the control flask under aseptic conditions. The flasks were incubated at 30^oC for 15 days on an incubator shaker (Heidolph Unimax 2010, USA) operated at 120 rpm. Each flask was analyzed for blended crude oil utilization at a 72 h interval. The indicators of blended petroleum utilization were; Total viable count, pH, turbidity and the residual Total Petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH).

Total viable bacterial count: Total viable bacterial counts of the respective flasks were determined by the pour plate method as described by Collins *et al.* (2004) with peptone water and Nutrient agar (NA) utilized as diluent and general purpose agar media of choice. Plating was carried out in duplicates and the agar plates were incubated at 37^oC for 24 h.

Evaluation of the *Penicillium* sp. biomass (dry weight): The resultant dry weight of the *Penicillium* sp. biomass at day 15 was determined by filtration of the fungal mycelia using a pre weighed filter paper and oven drying at 80 ^oC for 24 h (Nasim and Ali, 2011). The dry weight was then ascertained with the aid of a sensitive weigh balance (Al-Ghamdi, 2011).

Determination of pH: The pH of each culture flask was determined at a 72 h interval for 15 days with the aid of Suntext pH meter SP-701.

Determination of turbidity: This was also determined at a 72 h interval for 15 days. The parameter was analyzed with the aid of an HACH DR/2010 portable data logging spectrophotometer (HACH Co. Loveland, Colorado). Ten (10) ml of the sample was dispensed into a clean cuvette under aseptic conditions and steady turbidity readings were recorded at a wavelength of 810 nm.

Determination of the total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH) of the blended crude oil

The method as described by the American Petroleum Institute (API) (1968) was adapted to determine the Total Petroleum Hydrocarbon (TPH), Diesel Range Organics (DRO) of the blended crude oil layer of the respective culture flasks thrice within a period of 15 days. The TPH, (DRO) (C₈-C₄₀) content of the growth profile flasks was ascertained with the aid of a Hewlett Packard 5890 series II gas chromatograph (Hewlett Packard Co. Palo Alto, California). At the end of each run which lasted for 20-24 minutes, a computer generated result with a chromatogram and the concentration of the DRO was obtained.

Evaluation of the generation time, growth rate and %reduction of the TPH content of the crude oil by the axenic microbial cultures

The generation time and growth rate of the single bacterial isolates used in the growth profiling tests was calculated (Prescott *et al.*, 2005). Also the percentage reduction in the TPH (DRO) content of the sludge content of the respective flasks was also derived (Obayagbona and Enabulele, 2013).

Statistical analyses: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of the respective mean bacterial and fungal counts obtained from the soil samples was conducted ($\alpha= 0.05$) using SPSS version 17.0.

$$\text{Growth rate (day}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{\text{Difference in Cell counts}}{0.301 \times T} \quad ; \quad \text{Generation time (day)} = \frac{1}{\text{Growth rate}}$$

$$\% \text{ reduction of TPH} = \text{initial concentration} - \text{final concentration} = \text{reduction}$$

$$\% \text{ reduction of TPH} = \frac{\text{reduction}}{\text{Initial concentration}} \times 100$$

Duncan Multiple Range (DMR) test was conducted to locate the cause of any significant differences in the analyzed mean counts.

RESULTS

Table 1. shows that the mean total heterotrophic bacterial counts for the respective soils ranged from 0.4×10^3 cfu/g for N₁ to 1.5×10^3 cfu/g for N₃ respectively. The mean heterotrophic bacterial and fungal count recorded for the control soil sample was 2.2×10^3 cfu/g and 1.2×10^3 cfu/g respectively. The mean fungal counts ranged from 0.2×10^3 cfu/g for N₁ to 1.8×10^3 cfu/g for samples recently exposed to gas flaring activity (N₂). Heterotrophic fungal counts for soils obtained from the vicinity of the older gas flare pit ranged from 0.5×10^3 cfu/g for O₃ to 1.2×10^3 cfu/g for O₂ respectively. Mean hydrocarbon-utilizing bacterial counts recorded for the soil samples ranged from 0.1×10^3 cfu/g to 0.8×10^3 cfu/g for the soil samples sourced from the vicinities of both the new and old gas flare pits whilst the control soil had a count of 0.7×10^3 cfu/g. Also, mean hydrocarbon-utilizing fungal counts obtained from the soil samples ranged from 0.1×10^3 cfu/g to 0.7×10^3 cfu/g for soils collected in the vicinities of the gas flare pits while the control soil sample had a count of 0.9×10^3 cfu/g. The differences in the microbial counts were statistically significant ($P<0.05$) as a result of difference brought about by microbial counts recorded for N₁ and control soil sample.

Table 1: Total mean microbial counts and hydrocarbon-utilizing microbial counts of soil samples at gas flaring sites and control soil (cfu/g) $\times 10^3$

Soil Samples	Mean bacterial count (on NA)	Mean fungal count (on PDA)	Hydrocarbonoclastic bacterial counts (on MMSA)	Hydrocarbonoclastic fungal counts (on MMSA)
N ₁	^a 0.4	^a 0.2	^a 0.2	^a 0.2
N ₂	^b 1.3	^b 1.8	^b 0.8	^b 0.1
N ₃	^b 1.5	^b 1.6	^b 0.3	^b 0.3
O ₁	^b 0.4	^b 0.6	^b 0.7	^b 0.7
O ₂	^b 0.9	^b 1.2	^b 0.4	^b 0.2
O ₃	^b 1.1	^b 0.5	^b 0.1	^b 0.3
Control	^a 2.2	^a 1.2	^a 0.7	^a 0.9

Legend: N₁ – N₃: Soil samples that had just been recently exposed to gas flaring activities (for a period of 14 months) as at the sampling period. O₁ – O₃: Soil samples that been exposed to gas flaring activities (over a period of 7 years) prior to commencement of sampling. NA: Nutrient Agar, PDA: Potato Dextrose Agar, MMSA: Modified Mineral Salt Agar, Mean counts preceded by alphabet “b” are not significantly different (P>0.05) from each other using Duncan Multiple Range test, Mean counts preceded by alphabet “a” are significantly different (P<0.05) from each other using Duncan Multiple Range test.

The ten (10) bacterial isolates identified from the soil samples were: *Aeromonas* sp., *Bacillus* sp., *Serratia marcescens*, *Corynebacterium* sp., *Bacillus subtilis*, *Erdwardsiellatarda*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Flavobacterium* sp., *Citrobacter diversus* and *Klebsiella planticola*. *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus pumilus* had the highest percentage frequencies of isolation (85.7% each) as they were recovered from all the soil samples with the exception of N₁ and O₂ respectively. *Serratia marcescens*, *Erdwardsiellatarda* and *Flavobacterium* sp. recorded the lowest frequencies of isolation (28.6% each) as each isolate was only present in two (2) soil samples respectively (Table 2). Ten (10) fungal isolates were obtained from the soil samples; *Aspergillus versicolor*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Neurospora* sp., *Emericellanidulans*, *Curvularia* sp., *Mucor* sp., *Penicillium chrysogenum*, *Penicillium* sp., *Penicillium candidum*

Table 2: Prevalence of microbial isolates in the investigated soil samples

Isolates	N ₁	N ₂	N ₃	O ₁	O ₂	O ₃	Control	% Frequency of isolation
BACTERIA								
<i>Aeromonas</i> sp	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	57.1
<i>Bacillus</i> sp	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	71.4
<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	28.6
<i>Corynebacterium</i> sp	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	57.1
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	85.7
<i>Erdwardsiellatarda</i>	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	28.6
<i>Bacillus pumilus</i>	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	85.7
<i>Flavobacterium</i> sp	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	28.6
<i>Citrobacter diversus</i>	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	57.1
<i>Klebsiella planticola</i>	-	-	+	-	+	-	+	42.9
FUNGI								
<i>Aspergillus versicolor</i>	-	+	+	-	+	-	+	57.1
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	85.7
<i>Neurospora</i> sp	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	71.4
<i>Emericellanidulans</i>	-	-	+	-	+	-	+	42.9
<i>Curvularia</i> sp	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	28.6
<i>Mucor</i> sp	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	71.4
<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	71.4
<i>Penicillium</i> sp	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	85.7
<i>Penicillium candidum</i>	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	42.9
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	71.4

Legend:+: present , -: absent

and *Aspergillus flavus*. Amongst these isolates, *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium* sp. had the highest frequencies of isolation (85.7% each) as they were present in all the soil samples except O₃, control and N₃ respectively (Table 2).

The pH of the analyzed soils ranged from 5.90 to 7.20 respectively. Total nitrogen and cation exchange capacity values varied from 6.33 mg/kg to 12.99 mg/kg and 3.64 Meq/100g to 10.25 Meq/100g respectively (Table 3). The total organic carbon and moisture content of the soils had values which ranged from 4.74% to 5.52% and 2.14% to 11.04% respectively (Table 3). All the soils were sandy (Table 3) and cadmium was not detected in all the soil samples (Table 3).

Table 3: Physicochemical properties of the soil samples

Soil Sample	pH	Total N ₂ (mg/kg)	CEC (Meq/100g)	TOC (%)	THC (mg/l)	Moisture (%)	PARTICLE SIZE (%)			HEAVY METALS (mg/kg)		
							Sand	Silt	Clay	Pb	Zn	Cd
O ₁	6.50	9.15	8.45	5.28	0.54	6.95	60.00	32.60	7.40	ND	0.07	ND
O ₂	6.50	10.22	6.93	5.40	2.31	11.04	59.00	4.60	36.40	ND	ND	ND
O ₃	7.20	8.75	7.32	5.46	1.68	5.81	65.00	3.60	31.40	ND	ND	ND
N ₁	6.80	9.70	7.67	5.52	1.12	2.14	55.80	32.00	12.20	ND	0.08	ND
N ₂	6.90	8.51	6.26	5.37	1.14	3.39	57.20	7.00	35.80	ND	0.15	ND
N ₃	5.90	12.29	3.64	4.74	0.12	9.51	64.80	4.20	31.00	0.02	0.22	ND
Control	6.40	6.33	10.25	4.86	0.05	6.88	51.80	7.20	41.00	ND	0.11	ND

Legend: O₁-O₃: Soil samples that had been exposed to gas flaring activities (over a period of 7 years) as at the sampling period. N₁-N₃: Soil samples that had been recently exposed to gas flaring activities (over a period of 14 months) as at the sampling period. TOC: Total Organic Carbon, THC: Total Hydrocarbon content, CEC: Cation Exchange Capacity, Total N₂: Total Nitrogen, ND: Not Detected, Pb: Lead, Cd: Cadmium, Zn: Zinc.

All the bacterial isolates except *Bacillus subtilis*, *Serratia marcescens*, *Flavobacterium* sp., *Citrobacter diversus*, *Klebsiella planticola* and fungal isolates except *Neurospora* sp. and *Emericellanidulans* could utilize crude oil as energy source (Table 4). However, amongst the hydrocarbonoclastic bacterial isolates, *Aeromonas* sp., *Bacillus* sp., *Corynebacterium* sp. and the bacterial consortium had the best biodegradation potential as they effected the fastest color change (Table 4). Also, amongst the fungal isolates that were able to utilize crude oil, *Penicillium* sp. was recorded to have the best biodegradation potential (Table 4)

Table 4: Crude oil utilizing capabilities of isolates

Microbial isolates	2,6 DCIP reaction	Microbial isolates	2,6 DCIP reaction
<i>Aeromonas</i> sp.	Colorless after 24 h	<i>Aspergillus versicolor</i>	Colorless after 96 h
<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	Colorless after 24 h	<i>Neurospora</i> sp.	Blue after 158 h
<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	Blue after 158 h	<i>Curvularia</i> sp.	Colorless after 124 h
<i>Corynebacterium</i> sp.	Colorless after 24 h	<i>Mucor</i> sp.	Colorless after 72 h
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	Blue after 158 h	<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	Colorless after 24 h
<i>Edwardsiellatarda</i>	Colorless after 72 h		
<i>Bacillus pumilus</i>	Colorless after 96 h	<i>Penicillium candidum</i>	Colorless after 124 h
<i>Flavobacterium</i> sp.	Blue after 158 h	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	Colorless after 72 h

<i>Citrobacter diversus</i>	Blue after 158 h	<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>	Colorless after 72 h
<i>Klebsiella planticola</i>	Blue after 158 h	Bacterial Consortium	Colorless after 24 h
		Fungal Consortium	Colorless after 72 h

Corynebacterium sp. exhibited the highest growth rate (Table 5) whilst *Aeromonas* sp had the least growth rate during the growth profile study (Table 5).

Table 5: Growth rate (day^{-1}) and Generation time (days) of the single microbial isolates grown on crude oil- mineral salt medium.

Isolates	Growth rate (day^{-1})	Generation time (days)
<i>Aeromonas</i> sp.	15.3	* 8.2×10^{-8}
<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	15.7	3.3×10^{-8}
<i>Corynebacterium</i> sp.	15.9	4.9×10^{-8}
Bacterial Consortium	ND	ND
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	ND	ND
Control	ND	ND

Legend: *: Value approximated to the nearest decimal place

Aeromonas sp. effected the maximal reduction in the TPH (DRO) content of the blended crude oil portion of the culture medium (Table 6) whilst the consortium of bacterial isolates caused the least reduction in the TPH (DRO) content of the blended crude oil during the growth profile test (Table 6).

Table 6: Total Petroleum Hydrocarbon (Diesel Range Organics) mg/kg TPH (DRO) and % TPH reduction values of the respective pure microbial isolates grown on crude oil-mineral salt medium.

Isolates	Day 0	Day 9	Day 15	%TPH(DRO) reduction
<i>Aeromonas</i> sp.	14*	8	0	98
<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	14	4	1	92
<i>Corynebacterium</i> sp.	14	1	1	95
Bacterial Consortium	14	5	2	86
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	14	5	1	93
Control	14	3	1	94

Legend: *: Approximated value to the nearest whole number, TPH: Total Petroleum Hydrocarbon, DRO: Diesel Range Organics

The highest pH values were recorded for the bacterial consortium and *Penicillium* sp. at the first day 0 (Table 7), whilst the least pH reading was recorded for *Corynebacterium* sp. at day 15 (Table 7).

Table 7: pH of both single and mixed microbial cultures on Forcados blended crude oil-mineral salt medium

Isolates	Day 0	Day 3	Day 6	Day 9	Day 12	Day 15
<i>Aeromonas</i> sp.	7.2	7.2	6.8	6.9	6.2	6
<i>Corynebacterium</i> sp.	7.2	6.9	6.4	6.4	6.1	5.8
<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	7.2	7.2	6.4	6.3	6	5.9
Bacterial consortium	7.3	7.1	6.9	6.9	6.8	6.3
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	7.3	7	7	6.9	6.6	6.3
Control	7.2	7.2	7	6.9	6.9	6.8

The maximal turbidity value was recorded for *Bacillus* sp. at day 4 (Table 6), while the control flask had the least turbidity at day 12 (Table 8).

Table 8: Turbidity of both single and mixed microbial cultures on Forcados blended crude oil-mineral salt medium

Isolates	Day 0	Day 3	Day 6	Day 9	Day 12	Day 15
<i>Aeromonas</i> sp.	*38	19	48	41	30	78
<i>Corynebacterium</i> sp.	46	27	57	34	18	86
<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	46	26	91	43	47	84
Bacterial consortium	39	28	74	46	37	42
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	27	48	28	21	39	45
Control	72	16	20	15	2	10

Legend: * Values are given as Formazin Attenuation Unit (FAU)

The highest mean colony count was recorded for *Corynebacterium* sp. at day 15 (Table 9) while the lowest mean colony count was recorded for both the consortium of bacterial isolates and *Aeromonas* sp. at day 0 of the growth profile test (Table 9). The final dry weight of the harvested mycelium of *Penicillium* sp. was 3.6 g (Table 9).

Table 9: Mean colony counts of both single and mixed bacterial cultures, dry weight of *Penicillium* sp. grown on Forcados blended crude oil-mineral salt medium

Isolates	Day 0	Day 3	Day 6	Day 9	Day 12	Day 15
<i>Aeromonas</i> sp.	9×10^3	4.0×10^4	6.1×10^4	5.4×10^4	4.6×10^4	7.8×10^4
<i>Corynebacterium</i> sp.	1.4×10^4	3.7×10^4	6.2×10^4	4.6×10^4	6.2×10^4	8.6×10^4
<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	1.3×10^4	2.9×10^4	3.3×10^4	3.1×10^4	4.5×10^4	8.4×10^4
Bacterial consortium	0.9×10^4	2.1×10^4	3.3×10^4	7.0×10^4	5.3×10^4	6.1×10^4
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	[^] 3.6
Control	nil	Nil	nil	nil	nil	nil

Legend: *Values are given as colony forming units per millimeter (cfu.ml), ^ Value given as grams (g), ND: Not Determined

DISCUSSION

The bacterial and fungal counts recorded from soils exposed to gas flaring activities could be a reflection of the adaptive abilities of these microbial isolates to thrive even in the presence of air pollutants of various types and quantities on these soil surfaces over a period of time. However, the range of heterotrophic bacterial counts observed (Table 1) contrasted with a report by Ubani and Onyejekwe, (2013) which stated a range of counts; 1.1×10^2 cfu/g to 4.3×10^5 cfu/g for soils obtained at varying distances from several gas flare sites located in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. The recovery of hydrocarbon-utilizing microbial species from the control soil (Table 1), using modified mineral salt agar could suggest that hydrocarbonoclastic microorganisms are ubiquitous in the environment. The high frequency of occurrence of *Bacillus* spp. especially *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus pumilus* in all the soil samples with the exception of N₁ and O₂ respectively (Table 2), was not surprising as *Bacillus* spp. are widely distributed in many natural habitats (Cullimore, 2000). They possess endospores which are easily distributed through the atmosphere and possess unusual resistance to chemical and physical agents (Prescott *et al.* 2005). Bacteria from the genera *Aeromonas*, *Bacillus* and *Corynebacterium* have been found to be able to degrade aromatic hydrocarbons and have been isolated mainly from soils (Neilson and Allard, 1998). The highest percentage frequencies of occurrence for the fungal isolates were recorded for *Penicillium* sp. and *Aspergillus niger* as they were present in all the soil samples with the

exception of N₃, O₂ and Control (Table 2). This could be a reflection of the fact that these imperfect fungi are ubiquitous saprophytes, with easily dispersible conidiospores, commonly present wherever organic material is available. Also, *Penicillium* spp. have shown potentials for use in bioremediation because of their ability to break down a variety of xenobiotic compounds (Leitão, 2009). The pH of all the soil samples with the exception of O₂, N₁ and N₂ were acidic, with values ranging from 5.9 for N₃ to 7.3 for O₃ (Table 3). This observation is similar to those observed by Nwaugo *et al.* (2006) who reported a range of pH values (5.9-7.5) for topsoil samples obtained from gas flaring sites in parts of Niger Delta region of Southern Nigeria. The total organic carbon (TOC) values ranged from 4.74% in N₃ to 5.52% in N₁ and were relatively higher than those reported by Amund, (2000). The soil samples were generally sandy as revealed by the particle size analyses of the samples (Table 3). The concentrations of all the heavy metals (Pb, Cd and Zn) recorded for individual soil samples were similar to a report by Atoyebi and Akinde (2012) which reported heavy metal concentrations which ranged from 0.02mg/kg for Zinc to 0.52mg/kg for Lead. Some of the microbial isolates and consortium caused a color change in the incorporated 2, 6 DCIP- mineral salt medium at varying times (Table 4). This color change was attributed to the reduction of the indicator (2, 6 DCIP) by the oxidized products of hydrocarbon degradation (George-Okafor *et al.*, 2009). There was no correlation between the growth rate of the axenic microbial isolates and the consequent reduction in the residual TPH (DRO) content of the blended crude oil effected by these isolates. This is evident as despite the fact that *Corynebacterium* sp. had the maximal growth rate with *Aeromonas* sp. exhibiting the least growth rate (Table 5), *Aeromonas* sp. effected the maximal reduction in the TPH (DRO) content of the blended crude oil portion of the culture medium (Table 6). This trend is similar to an observation by Odjadjare *et al.*, (2008), which stated that there was no significant correlation between the specific growth rate of axenic bacterial isolates grown on Escarvos light crude oil (ELCO) and the extent of biodegradation of ELCO. Okoh *et al.*, (2001), suggested that the effect of the interactions of various components within the oil matrix on microbial metabolic activities could be responsible for this trend. Also, specific growth rate and biomass were required only to a particular threshold, enough to produce the appropriate enzyme system to carry through the degradation process; at this level, reduction or increase in biomass will have little or no effect on the overall degradation process (Johnsen *et al.* 2005). Comparatively, all the axenic microbial cultures were better degraders of the Forcados blended crude oil than the bacterial consortium employed (Table 5). This observation is also in agreement with an earlier report by Odjadjare *et al.*, (2008), which stated that single bacterial isolates were better than mixed bacterial cultures in degrading ELCO. This trend might be the result of the involvement of common genes/enzymes whose activities might be self-regulating (Johnsen *et al.* 2005).

The growth profiles of the single microbial cultures and bacterial consortium during the growth profile study showed continuous drop in pH (Table 7) accompanied by a decrease in the TPH (DRO) content of the inoculated blended crude oil (Table 6). This could reflect the fact that there were chemical changes in the hydrocarbon substrates as a result of enzymatic activities (Atlas and Bartha, 1998). There was a continuous increment in the turbidity of the respective

culture flasks during both growth profile tests (Table 8), with a concomitant steady increase in the colony count of the inoculated flasks (Table 9). These trends could suggest that the inoculated microbial isolates were able to grow on the crude oil as a sole carbon source and increase their submerged biomass resulting in an increment in the turbidity values of the liquid medium. Despite the absence of hydrocarbonoclastic microbial cultures in the control flask, there was an observed percentage reduction in the residual TPH (DRO) concentration of the sludge content of the flask (Table 6). This event might be attributed to abiotic degradation mechanisms as the control flasks were continuously agitated under daylight conditions at ambient temperatures ($28 \pm 2^{\circ}$ C), alongside the other labeled flasks for 15 days using the mechanical shaker. Many prominent abiotic degradative processes occur due to the influences of light (photolysis) and water (hydrolysis) (Leblance, 2004).

CONCLUSION

Soils surrounding the gas flare pits are a viable source of hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria and fungi. These microorganisms can be applied in bioremediation activities aimed at cleaning up several hydrocarbon pollutants, especially crude oil and its refined products, from both aquatic and terrestrial environments.

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